

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

SECOND-STEP LECTOTYPIIFICATION OF *CINNAMOMUM CAUDATUM*, THE BASIONYM OF *NEOCINNAMOMUM CAUDATUM* (LAURACEAE)

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ABSTRACT

A second-step lectotype has been designated for *Cinnamomum caudatum* Nees, the basionym of *Neocinnamomum caudatum* (Nees) Merr.

Key words: Lauraceae, *Neocinnamomum*, lectotypification.

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INTRODUCTION

The genus *Neocinnamomum* H. Liu comprises 7 species, distributed in Bhutan, Nepal, India, Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, Vietnam, China and Indonesia (POWO, 2025). *Cinnamomum caudatum* Nees, the basionym of *Neocinnamomum caudatum* (Nees) Merr., was described from Nepal based on a single gathering, Wallich 2603. The species is now known to occur in Bhutan, Nepal, Northeast India, Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, Vietnam and China (POWO, 2025). Kostermans (1969) cited the type as: “typus *Wallich* 2603 (K).” This was an effective lectotypification as per Art. 7.11 (Turland *et al.*, 2025). Subsequently, Kostermans (1974) again cited the type as: “Typus: *Wallich* Cat. 2603, fl. (BM, BO, K).” This second designation has no effect on his first designation as per Art. 9.19 (Turland *et al.*, 2025). Reference to Kew herbarium reveals that two duplicates of the collection, Wallich 2603, are available bearing the barcodes K001116545 (in the Wallich’s herbarium, K-W) and K000228445 (in the general herbarium). None of these sheets bear any annotation by Kostermans indicating which specimen was chosen by him as the “type”. Thus, this situation represents a first-step lectotypification by Kostermans (1969) according to Art. 9.17 of the Code (Turland *et al.*, 2025). Hence, a second-step lectotype of the name is designated here for which the better specimen out of the two at K is chosen which agrees well with the protologue.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation is based on the study of literature and types specimens available online at B, BM, E, G, GZU, K, L and MO.

LECTOTYPIIFICATION

Neocinnamomum caudatum (Nees) Merr. in Contr. Arnold Arbor. 8: 64. 1934. – *Cinnamomum caudatum* Nees in Wall., Pl. Asiat. Rar. 2: 76. 1831.

Type (lectotype, first-step designated by Kostermans, 1969, p. 287; second-step designated here): Nepal, 1820, Wallich Numer. List No. 2603 (K001116545, digital image! isoelectotypes B_10_0277545, B_10_0277546, B_10_0277547, BM000950953, BM000950954, E00393325, E00393326, G00693891, GZU000253936, K000228445, L0037079, L0037080, L0037081, MO-247425, digital images!).

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Authors do not have any conflicts of interest.

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